

Predictors of adverse perinatal outcome up to 34 weeks, a multivariable analysis study.

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Ultrasound predictor of adverse perinatal outcome until 34 weeks.

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ABSTRACT

Objective

To evaluate the best ultrasound predictors of adverse perinatal outcome (APO) in fetuses examined up to 34 weeks and delivered by spontaneous or induced labor.

Methods

This was a retrospective study of 129 pregnancies that underwent an ultrasound Doppler examination at 23-34 weeks and entered into labor within 30 days. Umbilical artery pulsatility index (UA PI), middle cerebral artery PI (MCA PI), cerebroplacental ratio (CPR) and mean uterine artery pulsatility index (mUtA PI) were converted into multiples of the median (MoM) and estimated fetal weight (EFW) into centiles to adjust for gestational age (GA). Sonographic and clinical parameters were evaluated using logistic regression analysis.

Results

The multivariable model for the prediction of APO presented an area under the curve of 0.82. Significant predictors were EFW centile, GA, MCA PI MoM, and CPR (if this was considered instead of its individual components). In addition, when more objective criteria for intrapartum hypoxia were applied, CPR became the only predictor of APO, with similar prediction ability (AUC 0.76).

Conclusion

Up to 34 weeks, prediction of APO can be done evaluating EFW and fetal cerebral flow. No added benefit is obtained examining the mUtA PI.

KEY WORDS

Cerebroplacental ratio, umbilical artery Doppler, middle cerebral artery Doppler, uterine artery Doppler, adverse perinatal outcome.

INTRODUCTION

The final goal of ultrasound at the third trimester is the prediction of adverse perinatal outcome (APO)¹. Despite this examination was initially questioned by some studies², the last evidence has supported its efficacy as a screening test³, with an accuracy that improves in parallel to gestational age (GA) and inversely to the interval examination-labor^{4,5}.

At the latter weeks of pregnancy, due to the special physiopathology of late-onset fetal growth restriction (FGR), cerebroplacental ratio (CPR), which combines information from cerebral flow and placental resistance, has become the best test for outcome prediction⁶⁻⁸, making unnecessary to interrogate the mean uterine artery pulsatility index (mUt PI) and the ductus venosus PI (DV PI).

Conversely, earlier in pregnancy, FGR is caused by placental disease causing progressive hemodynamic changes⁹⁻¹⁰. Unfortunately, despite these changes have been exhaustively described, information about which are the best predictors of APO is still scarce. This study was aimed to define these predictors in women attempting vaginal delivery prior to 34 weeks.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This was a retrospective study of 129 single fetuses attending at the maternity of three tertiary hospitals in Valencia, Madrid and Rome. Ultrasound examinations were performed between 23⁺⁴ and 34⁺⁴ weeks using a GA determined according to the crown-rump length in the first trimester. They included an estimated fetal weight and a Doppler evaluation of the umbilical (UA) PI, middle cerebral arteries (MCA) PI, mUtA PI and CPR. The UA, MCA and mUtA PI were recorded using color and pulsed Doppler according to earlier descriptions¹¹⁻¹³. In some of the fetuses, Doppler examination was done in interest of research. In others it was done in fetuses with risk factors such as abnormal uterine Doppler, reduced fetal movements or diagnosis of FGR. Non-Caucasian cases were discarded in order to avoid ethnicity heterogeneity and only one (the last) examination per fetus was included. Only cases in which labor started within 1 month (30 days interval) after examination were included. Finally, multiple pregnancies and pregnancies complicated by congenital fetal abnormalities or aneuploidy were excluded.

Because we were interested in labor outcome after induction or spontaneous onset, severe cases of FGR (those with absent or reverse diastolic umbilical flow, abnormal ductus venosus pulsatility index (DV PI) or abnormal cardiotocography (CTG) that ended with cesarean section (CS)) were discarded, including only appropriate for gestational age (AGA) fetuses, small for gestational age fetuses and fetuses with mild FGR, that were a priori able to stand spontaneous or induced labor. Therefore, all cases had in common that fetuses were hemodynamically submitted to the stress of labor and attempted vaginal delivery.

In order to adjust for the effect of the gestational age (GA), estimated fetal weight (EFW), and birth weight (BW) values were converted into centiles. This conversion was done according to references earlier published¹⁴ or using online calculator or specific Excel calculators provided by the original authors. Local population references were adjusted for fetal gender, so gender was not considered afterwards as a variable for the multivariable analysis as it was included in the centile. Also, UA PI, MCA PI, mUtA PI and CPR values were converted into multiples of median (MoM) dividing each value by the 50th centile at each gestational age as earlier described¹¹⁻¹³. UA PI, MCA PI and mUtA PI medians (50th centiles) were represented by the equations¹¹⁻¹³:

$$\text{UA PI } 50^{\text{th}} \text{ centile} = 2.2037 - 0.057955 * \text{GA} + 0.00053953 * \text{GA}^2$$

$$\text{MCA PI } 50^{\text{th}} \text{ centile} = -3.266164164 + 0.368135209 * \text{GA} - 0.006318278 * \text{GA}^2$$

$$\text{mUtA } 50^{\text{th}} \text{ centile} = 2.0116 - 0.064333 * \text{GA} + 0.00075757 * \text{GA}^2$$

$$\text{CPR } 50^{\text{th}} \text{ centile} = -3.814786276 + 0.36363249 * \text{GA} - 0.005646672 * \text{GA}^2$$

Where GA was gestational age in weeks with decimals.

All Doppler examinations were performed by certified experts in obstetric ultrasound, using General Electric Voluson[®] (E8/E6/730) and Toshiba Aplio 500 ultrasound machines with 2-8 MHz convex probes, during fetal quiescence, in the absence of fetal tachycardia, and keeping the insonation angle with the examined vessels as small as possible.

Gestational characteristics including parity, number of gestations and maternal ethnicity, age, pre-pregnancy weight and height, were collected at examination. In addition, labor outcome data including BW, mode of delivery, Apgar score, cord arterial pH and admission to the neonatal care unit were collected after birth to evaluate APO. This was considered when the outcome was adverse for any of these components: abnormal intrapartum fetal heart rate (according to the intrapartum fetal monitoring guidelines of the FIGO)¹⁵, or intrapartum fetal scalp pH <7.20 requiring expedite delivery by the fastest route, neonatal umbilical cord pH <7.10, 5 minute Apgar score <7, and postpartum admission to the neonatal intensive care unit or special care baby unit. As per local protocol, all fetuses were initially aimed to reach a vaginal delivery but were subsequently managed according to their progression in labor. Doppler examinations did not influence management of labors, which were performed by different obstetricians. Importantly, cases with abnormal intrapartum fetal heart rate ending with instrumental delivery were not included as APO if fetal scalp pH or neonatal pH were within the normal limits.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics were performed evaluating maternal age, parity, GA at examination in weeks, GA at delivery in weeks, interval between ultrasound and delivery, EFW, EFW centile, Doppler parameters (UA PI, MCA PI, UtA PI, UA PI MoM, MCA PI MoM, UtA PI MoM), fetal gender, onset of labor (induction and spontaneous), mode of delivery (CS, forceps, vacuum (ventouse), Thierry's spatulas spontaneous vaginal delivery), Apgar scores at 5 minutes, neonatal cord arterial pH, and baby destiny (maternity ward, neonates ward, intensive care unit). Continuous variables were presented as median and interquartile range (IQR), while categorical variables were presented as absolute and relative frequencies. Descriptive statistics

were also evaluated comparing those fetuses that presented APO from those that did not present APO.

The accuracies and relative importance of the MCA PI MoM, UA PI MoM, mUtA PI MoM, CPR MoM and EFW centile for the detection of APO were subsequently evaluated with multivariable logistic regression analysis, describing the estimate, the odds ratio (OR) (or exponent of the estimate, an indicator of the importance of the parameter), the p-value, the ROC curve with the area under the curve (AUC) and the detection rate (DR) (or sensitivity) for a false positive rate (FPR) (1-specificity) of 5 and 10%. ROC-AUC was validated by bootstrap internal validation¹⁶. Parameters were evaluated alone and combined with clinical information known at examination (maternal age, pre-pregnancy weight, height, number of gestations, parity, smoking habit and GA at examination). Using these variables, two multivariable logistic regression models were created evaluating either MCA PI + UA PI or CPR.

Finally, in order to avoid the influence of prematurity on APO, we performed another multivariable logistic regression analysis including CPR MoM, which evaluated the prediction of APO including only parameters more objectively related with fetal hypoxia, such as abnormal cardiotocogram, intrapartum pH requiring expedite delivery and neonatal pH <7.10.

Comparisons were made with Wilcoxon for continuous variables and Chi-Square test for categorical variables. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) was used to evaluate prediction models by means of a lower AIC, which indicated the presence of a higher accuracy (a difference in the AIC of 2 units indicated significant differences and a difference of 2-4 units indicated highly significant differences). There is generally a tradeoff between goodness of fit and parsimony: low parsimony models (i.e. models with many parameters) tend to have a better fit than high parsimony models. However, adding more parameters usually results in a good model fit for the data at hand, but that same model will likely be useless for predicting other data sets. The AIC allows a good balance between parsimony and goodness of fit.

In the models we included the Somers Dxy Rank Correlation (Dxy). Statistically, Somers D correlation between a variable x and a binary (0-1) variable y, and the corresponding receiver operating characteristic curve area c, corresponds to the formula: $2*(c - 0.5)$ which represents the difference in the probability that predictions are concordant with outcomes minus the probability that they are discordant.

Statistical analysis and graphs were performed using the R-software® (version 3.3.2). Significance was considered with a p-value of less than 0.05. Institutional Review Board permission was obtained for this study (Reference 2014/0063). The authors report no conflict of interests.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the characteristics of the study population. In summary, the study included 129 fetuses, of which 48% were male and 52% female. The mean maternal age was 33 years, and the mean GA at examination and delivery were 32.4 and 34.8 weeks. Most of the pregnancies had an induced onset of labor (67.4%) and a spontaneous vaginal delivery (59.7%), with neonates born uneventfully and sent with the mother to the maternity ward (44.2%). The main indication for labor induction was FGR, hypertension including preeclampsia and premature rupture of membranes. In agreement with this high-risk profile, 45% (N=58) of all induced cases were below the 10th centile. Concerning delivery, only 5.4 % had an Apgar score <7 at 5 minutes, while 3.9% had a neonatal cord pH <7.10 and 55.8% needed admission to postnatal pediatric care. The proportion of fetuses below the 10th centile in the study population was 56.6% according to the study time interval and tertiary nature of the center (many cases were referred from other centers to induce labor). In fact, 62.8% of the study population ended up presenting an APO.

Table 2 shows the characteristics of the pregnancies according to the study outcome. In summary, mothers in the APO group (N=81) presented similar somatometries than those in the normal outcome group but presented a lower number of previous gestations (p=0.04) and parity (p= 0.026). In addition, when compared to the fetuses with normal outcome, the UA PI (p<0.0001), UA PI MoM (P=0.001), Mean UtA PI (p=0.015), Mean UtA PI MoM (P= 0.04) were significantly higher, while the MCA PI (p=0.011), MCA PI MoM (p=0.007), CPR (p<0.0001) and CPR MoM (p=0.001) were significantly lower. There were also significant differences in the GA at examination (p=0.001), GA at labor (p<0.0001), interval examination-labor (p<0.0001), EFW (p<0.0001), EFW centiles (p<0.0001), BW (P<0.0001), BW centiles (p=0.003), neonatal ward admission (p<0.0001), and in the frequency of CS for abnormal CTG (p<0.0001), proportion of SGA (p= 0.004), Apgar score at 5 minutes and Apgar score <5 at 5 minutes (p<0.0001) and neonatal cord pH <7.10 (p<0.0001).

Table 3 and figure 1 show the multivariable model that combines sonographic parameters (UA PI MoM, MCA PI MoM; mUt PI MoM and EFW centiles) with clinical and maternal characteristics. The model showed an AUC of 0.823 (95% CI 0.753-0.893) and a DR of 50.6% and 56.8% for a FPR of 5% and 10%. Significant predictors of APO were the MCA PI MoM (OR 0.05, 95% CI 0.003-0.698), EFW

centile (OR 0.983, 95% CI 0.967-0.998) and GA at examination (OR 0.503, 95% CI 0.29-0.741). Interestingly, no clinical data was significant for APO prediction.

When CPR was included instead of UA PI MoM and MCA PI MoM (table 4, figure 1) the model presented an AUC of 0.814 (95% CI 0.742-0.886); DR were of 49.38% and 53.09% for a FPR of 5% and 10%. Significant predictors of APO were in this case the CPR MoM (OR 0.121, 95% CI 0.019-0.63), EFW centile (OR 0.982, 95% CI 0.967-0.996) and GA at examination (OR 0.51, 95% CI 0.302-0.748). The model achieved a similar accuracy than the model combining individual parameters (AIC 150.84 versus AIC 149.88).

Finally, when we used a simplified APO including only stricter parameters related with fetal hypoxia (table 5, figure 2) the model presented an AUC of 0.765 (95% CI 0.666-0.863); DR were of 24.24% and 42.42% for a FPR of 5% and 10%. Significant predictors of APO were in this case only the CPR MoM (OR 0.127, 95% CI 0.021-0.75).

DISCUSSION

Summary of findings

The findings of this study show that prior to 34 weeks and within 30 days of labor, perinatal outcome notably associates with changes of cerebral flow.

Interpretation of the findings

Despite the different physiopathology of early and late FGR¹⁷, adverse labor outcome below 34 weeks is still importantly explained by cerebral flow, resembling to some extent the scenario at late pregnancy, when outcome is mainly predicted by CPR (and to a lesser extent EFW) and not by mUtA PI^{6,7}. The importance of the cerebral flow prior to 34 weeks confirms that it behaves as a significant and reliable predictor of APO at any GA. Moreover, according to its OR, the EFW proved to perform again worse than CPR (or MCA PI) in the prediction of APO, similarly to late pregnancy when it has been proven to perform below any Doppler parameter⁷. Finally, using a stricter APO directly related with fetal hypoxia we also proved that the importance of CPR was importantly associated with this condition and not with prematurity.

Comparison with existing literature

Regarding past references, we were unable to find multivariable studies evaluating predictors of delivery outcome in fetuses examined <34 weeks. Most of previous publications have solely studied the mUtA PI for the prediction of APO especially in preeclampsia¹⁸⁻²¹ or the CPR^{22,23} for the prediction of APO in an isolated way. In general, these studies confirm that lower values of CPR and high values of mUtA PI herald APO, although the mUtA PI effect is doubtful in case of AGA^{4,25}. The interesting aspect of our study was that Doppler parameters were studied at unison with clinical parameters and in a multivariate analysis, in order to ponder their relative importance. In this regard it is interesting to observe that the information coming from the cerebral flow is already important at the early third trimester and thus is not exclusive patrimony of examinations done in the late phase of pregnancy⁶. Another interesting aspect was that the study was limited to those fetuses a priori attempting spontaneous or induced labor. This required exclusion of severe FGR and elective CS of other causes, as they would preclude the true evaluation of labor outcome in those fetuses going through the stress of contractions.

Clinical implications

In fetuses examined early in the third trimester prediction of APO is notably achieved evaluating EFW plus cerebral flow (CPR and MCA PI). This proves that CPR and

MCA PI are good markers of APO, not only at the end of the third trimester (as previously thought) but also earlier in gestation. This might be used to classify preterm fetuses that attempt vaginal delivery, determining those that might be at risk for worse outcome.

Strengths and weaknesses

The strengths are its novelty, as there are no previous studies evaluating with multivariate analysis predictors of APO in fetuses a priori attempting vaginal delivery, the accurate statistical methodology, including the use of a stricter APO directly related with fetal hypoxia, and the heterogeneity of the study group, which positions cerebral vasodilation as a common end point for a variety of conditions causing APO. Conversely, shortcomings include the low number of cases, the relatively large interval examination-labor (although within a logic prediction interval), the absence of differentiation between different methods of induction²⁶ and the lack of long-term follow-up to define APO.

Conclusion

Up to 34 weeks, prediction of adverse perinatal outcome after spontaneous or induced labor may be done using the information provided by cerebral flow (MCA PI and CPR). However, the best prediction is achieved combining this information with EFW and GA.

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LEGENDS

Figure 1

Upper figure: ROC curves of the multivariable models shown in table 3 (including MCA PI MoM and UA PI MoM). AUC of 0.823 (95% CI 0.753-0.893); DR of 50.6% and 56.8% for a FPR of 5% and 10%.

Lower figure: ROC curves of the multivariable models shown in table 4 (including CPR MoM instead of its components). Results were similar: AUC of 0.814 (95% CI 0.742-0.886); DR of 49.38% and 53.09% for a FPR of 5% and 10%.

Figure 2

ROC curve of the multivariable model shown in table 5, including and APO related with fetal hypoxia and CPR MoM instead of its components: AUC of 0.765 (95% CI 0.666-0.863); DR of 24.24% and 42.42% for a FPR of 5% and 10%.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics according to the presence or absence of adverse perinatal outcome (APO).

				Normal outcome, N=48 (37.2%)				Adverse perinatal outcome**, N=81 (62.8%)					
				Mean	(SD)	Median	(1st, 3rd Q)	Mean	(SD)	Median	(1st, 3rd Q)		p-value
Maternal	age	(years)		33.21	6.69	34.5	(30, 38)	32.98	5.94	34	(30, 37)		0.843
Number	of	gestations		2.83	1.75	3	(1, 3.25)	2.22	1.33	2	(1, 3)		0.04
Parity				1.04	1.24	1	(0, 1)	0.59	0.77	0	(0, 1)		0.026
Maternal	pre-pregn	weight	(kg)	61.98	14.81	60	(51.75, 68)	64.1	13.61	63	(55, 70)		0.419
Maternal	Height	(cm)		159.4	7.31	160	(155.75, 163)	160.68	7.41	160	(155, 166)		0.34
GA	at	examinati	(weeks)	33.02	0.77	33.14	(32.57, 33.57)	32.05	2.35	32.86	(31.86, 33.57)		0.001
EFW	hadlock-4	(g)		1980	273.2	1955	(1780, 2140)	1612	447	1643	(1319, 1880)		<.0001
EFW	Local	Pop.	Ref. Cent	41.1	31.39	39	(12.5, 67.5)	20.65	27.91	9	(1, 26)		<.0001
MCA	PI			1.94	0.28	1.92	(1.73, 2.12)	1.78	0.4	1.8	(1.50, 2.08)		0.011
MCA	PI	MoM		0.97	0.14	0.95	(0.87, 1.05)	0.89	0.2	0.9	(0.75, 1.03)		0.007
UA	PI			0.97	0.18	0.98	(0.84, 1.08)	1.21	0.5	1.09	(0.89, 1.33)		<.0001
UA	PI	MoM		1.11	0.2	1.13	(0.98, 1.23)	1.34	0.54	1.18	(1, 1.49)		0.001
CPR				2.05	0.5	1.94	(1.73, 2.31)	1.67	0.64	1.75	(1.20, 2.01)		<.0001
CPR	MoM			1.01	0.24	0.95	(0.85, 1.13)	0.84	0.32	0.88	(0.59, 1.01)		0.001
Mean	UtA	PI		0.94	0.32	0.87	(0.70, 1.11)	1.11	0.45	1.03	(0.79, 1.34)		0.015
Mean	UtA	PI	MoM	1.32	0.46	1.23	(0.99, 1.52)	1.51	0.58	1.35	(1.04, 1.88)		0.04
GA	at	labour	(weeks)	36.2	1.1	36.2	(35.2, 37)	34.03	3.02	34.57	(32.57, 36.29)		<.0001
Interval	exam-lab	(days)		22.1	6.87	24	(18, 27.25)	13.84	9.96	15	(4, 23)		<.0001
Birth	weight	(g)		2428	320	2380	(2165, 2645)	1819	540.2	1875	(1470, 2180)		<.0001
BW	Local	Pop.	Ref. centi	29.13	30.45	16.5	(4, 43.7)	13.6	22.15	2	(0, 15)		0.003
Apgar	at	5 minutes		9.7	0.7	10	(9.2, 10)	8.84	1.54	9	(8, 10)		<.0001
				N (%)				N (%)					
Gender													0.095
Male				18	37.50%			44	54.30%				
Female				30	62.50%			37	45.70%				
BW	<10th	centile	(SGA)*	19	39.60%			54	66.70%				0.004
Apgar	5 min	<7		0	0%			7	8.60%				<.0001
Arterial	cord	pH	<7.10	0	0%			5	6.20%				<.0001
Smokers				10	20.80%			9	11.10%				0.211
Onset	of	labour											0.807
Induction	of	labour		33	68.70%			54	66.70%				
Spontaneous	onset	of	labour	15	31.25%			27	33.30%				
Via	of	labour											
Spontaneous	vaginal	delivery		40	83.30%			37	45.70%				<.0001
Assisted	vaginal	delivery		4	8.30%			3	3.70%				
Caesarean	section	abnormal	CTG	0	0%			32	39.50%				
Caesarean	section	dystocia		4	8.30%			9	11.10%				
Baby	destiny												<.0001
Maternity	ward			48	100%			9	11.10%				
Neonates	ward			0	0%			37	45.70%				
Intensive	care	paediatric	unit	0	0%			35	43.20%				

Table 2. Combined multivariate model using Doppler values in MoM, EFW centiles and maternal characteristics for the prediction of APO.

			Estimate	Std. Error	OR	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	p-value
Intercept			18.769					
Induction of labour			-0.564	0.525	0.569	0.203	1.592	NS
CPR	MoM		-2.167	0.881	0.114	0.02	0.644	<.05
Mean	UtA	PI MOM	0.057	0.492	1.059	0.403	2.779	NS
EFW	centiles		-0.019	0.008	0.981	0.966	0.995	<.05
GA	examination		-0.638	0.229	0.528	0.337	0.826	<.01
Maternal age			0.041	0.037	1.042	0.968	1.121	NS
Smoking (yes)			-0.832	0.59	0.435	0.137	1.385	NS
Number of gestations			0.042	0.24	1.042	0.651	1.67	NS
Parity			-0.640	0.389	0.527	0.246	1.131	NS
Pre-pregn weight			0.032	0.019	1.032	0.995	1.071	NS
Maternal height			0.017	0.032	1.017	0.954	1.084	NS
Model accuracy:	Detection rate of 39.5% for a FPR of 5% and 56.8% for a FPR of 10%, p < .0001.							
	ROC-AUC = 0.82, (95% CI 0.75–0.89).							

Table 3. Multivariate logistic regression analysis using individualised parameters: UA MoM, MCA MoM, mUtA PI MoM, EFW centile and maternal characteristics for the prediction of composite APO.

				Estimate	Std. Error	OR	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	p-value
Intercept				17.847					
Induction	of	labour		-0.570	0.533	0.565	0.199	1.606	NS
UA	PI	MoM		1.638	0.932	5.144	0.828	31.973	NS
MCA	PI	MoM		-2.982	1.41	0.05	0.003	0.804	<.05
Mean	UtA	PI	MoM	0.096	0.507	1.101	0.407	2.975	NS
EFW	centiles			-0.018	0.008	0.982	0.967	0.997	<.05
GA	examination			-0.648	0.233	0.523	0.331	0.825	<.01
Maternal	age			0.044	0.038	1.045	0.969	1.126	NS
Smoking	(yes)			-0.805	0.602	0.447	0.137	1.454	NS
Number	of	gestations		0.081	0.248	1.084	0.667	1.763	NS
Parity				-0.738	0.402	0.478	0.217	1.052	NS
Pre-pregnancy	weight			0.033	0.019	1.033	0.995	1.073	NS
Maternal	height			0.016	0.033	1.016	0.952	1.084	NS